

Metal Nitrene Chemistry

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This paper gives a brief review of the research done in our laboratory on the formation of metal nitrene (NH) complexes, and the reactivity of the coordinated nitrene. The complexes are formed as active intermediates by (1) the reaction of certain azido metal amines with acid, (2) the reactions of these systems photochemically, and (3) by the reaction of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ with bromide or hydroxide ions. The coordinated nitrene (M-NH) behaves as a powerful electrophile, reacting with even weak nucleophiles such as HSO_3^- and Cl^- to form the corresponding acidoamines (M-NH₂X).

NITRENE¹ is the term used for the electron-deficient electroneutral molecule NH and its derivatives.

The derivatives are formally produced by substitution of the hydrogen in NH. Consequently, organic nitrenes are either alkylnitrenes (R-N) or arylnitrenes (ϕ -N), and a metal nitrene is M-N. However, we also use metal nitrene for M-NH, in order to avoid having to always saying "nitrene coordinated to a metal". The term metal nitrene is also only applicable to these systems if the nitrogen ligand atom is known to behave as an electrophile. If it behaves as a nucleophile, as it does in most cases, then the species are called nitrido (M-N) or imido (M-NH) metal complexes (Fig 1).

Figure 1. Metal nitrene, where the coordinated ligand is singlet nitrene ($\ddot{\text{N}}-\text{H}$). Metal imide, where for the same system the electron pair localized on the metal in the nitrene is now localized on the nitrogen to give the imido ligand $\ddot{\text{N}}-\text{H}^{2+}$.

Organic nitrene chemistry is a large significant area of organic chemistry.¹ The same can not be said of inorganic nitrene chemistry. However, several reactions are known which involve cleavage of the MN-N₂ bond in metal azido systems. For example, isocyanato metal complexes are formed by the reactions of some metal carbonyls with azide ion,² or the reaction of azido metal complexes with carbon monoxide.³ None of these reactions appear to involve a metal nitrene. Kwart and Kahn⁴ were the first to suggest the formation of a metal nitrene intermediate. A copper nitrene path was proposed for the copper catalyzed decomposition of benzene sulfonylazide. Also Gleiter and Hoffman⁵ have suggested the stabilization of the electron deficient nitrene by coordination to transition metals.

Research in our laboratory on metal nitrenes started with the discovery by Bauer⁶ that *trans*- $\text{Ir}(\text{en})_2(\text{N}_3)_2^+$ readily reacts with acid to generate pure dinitrogen gas.

Subsequent studies indicate that this reaction takes place by means of a low energy metal nitrene path. A similar reaction path has been assigned to the photochemical reactions of certain azido metal amines, and to some of the reactions of coordinated chloramine.

Reactions of Azido Metal Complexes with Acid. The addition of aqueous acid to $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ causes the vigorous evolution of dinitrogen.⁷ This behavior is markedly different from that of most transition metal azides in acid. In general, acid merely catalyzes the displacement of coordinated azide ion as hydrazoic acid. For the action of H_2SO_4 on $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{N}_3)_2$, the products have been characterized by their ultraviolet spectra. Two intense bands were produced at 220 and 262 nm. Their wavelengths and intensities agree well with those reported for $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_2^{2+}$ and the dimer $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Ru}-\text{N}\equiv\text{N}-\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5^{4+}$ (A), respectively⁸. In 0.8 M H_2SO_4 , reaction is complete at room temperature within 5 min. This rapid appearance of nitrogen dimer(A) eliminates the possibility that it is produced by the combination of $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_2^{2+}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{2+}$. The rate of the latter reaction has been measured by Itzkovitch and Page⁹. Under the conditions employed here, such combination would require several hours.

The vigorous evolution of nitrogen and the rapid formation of a nitrogen-bridged dimer is reminiscent of the behavior of organic azides when treated with acid or ultraviolet radiation¹. A similar reaction pathway, involving a metalated nitrene (B), is proposed for the acid reaction of $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$, [eqs. (1) and (2)].

Strong support for the presence of the nitrene intermediate (B) was obtained from trapping experiments. In the presence of small amounts of thiourea, diethyl sulfide, or iodide ion, the reaction of acid on $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{N}_3)_2$ generated no dimer. This behavior may be rationalized in terms of the combination of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Ru}-\text{NH}^{\delta+}$ with itself to produce the dimer(A) being quenched by the more rapid reaction of the nitrene with the bases thiourea, diethyl sulfide, or I^- .

Note that the overall reaction of $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ with acid involves the facile reduction of Ru(III) to Ru(II). Since in these systems, Ir(II) is not a readily available oxidation state, it was of interest to investigate the reaction of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ with acid which also yields the gas dinitrogen.¹⁰ The results showed that the oxidation state of Ir(III) does not change, and that the redox reaction involves only the coordinated azido group (eq. 3).

Salts of the chloramine products have been isolated and characterized.

Kinetic studies were consistent with this iridium azido complex also reacting by a nitrene path, although the products differ from that of the corresponding ruthenium complex. Strong support that both Ir(III) and Ru(III) systems react by similar nitrene intermediates is provided by the observation that in the presence of $\text{HSO}_3^-/\text{SO}_3^{2-}$ both react to form the sulfamate products¹¹ (eq. 4).

Other reactions in accord with a nitrene intermediate for the I-III system are shown in Scheme I.

Scheme I

These reactions show that the coordinated nitrene behaves like an extremely powerful electrophile. Such behavior is expected for singlet nitrenes, in which a valence shell orbital is unoccupied, and is observed for the singlet aminonitrenes, $\text{R}_2\text{N}-\text{N}$.¹ When nitrene is produced photochemically from HN_3 in aqueous solutions, a process which should yield the singlet form, NH_2OH and NH_2Cl (in HCl) are the main products¹². Hence, the coordinated nitrene produced in this work shows behavior typical of singlet nitrenes.

These reactions of coordinated nitrene are novel and differ from those observed for the Ru(III) systems.⁷ The difference in behavior can be attributed to the ease of reduction of Ru(III) to Ru(II), a reaction pathway not available for Ir(III).

The action of acid on azido complexes often results in solvolysis of the complex, liberating HN_3 , rather than decomposition of the coordinated azide¹³. In many cases, this difference in behavior can be attributed to the lability of the metal-nitrogen bond and the poor coordinating ability of HN_3 . This explanation is not valid for the solvolysis^{13a} of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ to $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{2+}$, since the rate of solvolysis of this azido complex in acid is slower than the rate of decomposition of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ to $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}^{\delta+}$ under the same conditions. However, the difference can be attributed to a lowering of the energy of the transition state for nitrene formation by π donation from the filled t_{2g} orbitals on Ir(III). This explanation implies that the d orbital electrons are more available for π donation in Ir(III) than in Rh(III) and is in keeping with the observed increase in metal basicity going down a group in the periodic table.¹⁴ This $d\pi \rightarrow p\pi$ interaction is analogous to the $p\pi \rightarrow p\pi$ interaction which is invoked to explain the unusual stability and the singlet (rather than triplet) ground state of the aminonitrenes, $\text{R}_2\text{N}-\text{N}$.¹

Photochemical Reactions of Azido Metal Complexes: Investigations of the photolysis of several different azido-metal complexes suggest the formation of azido radical which then reacts with itself to generate nitrogen.¹⁵ However, this is not the photochemical behavior of the azido group for hydrozoic acid and for organic azides. The photolysis of hydrozoic acid yields the active intermediate nitrene (NH),¹⁶ and organic azides react photochemically to produce substituted nitrenes (NR).¹ Since a nitrene path had been observed for the reaction of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ with acid, it was decided to investigate the photochemistry of this complex and of the corresponding Rh(III) complex. This study led to the discovery¹⁷ of the first example of a photochemical decomposition of an azido metal complex by means of a nitrene path. The stoichiometry of the photochemical reaction in aqueous dilute hydrochloric acid was established¹⁸ to be that shown by eq. 5.

When a 0.1 *M* HCl solution of $[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ was exposed to ultraviolet radiation, 1 mol of nitrogen was evolved per mole of complex decomposed. The evolution of nitrogen was not quenched by either iodide ion or acrylamide, both of which quench the evolution of nitrogen for photochemical reactions of azido metal complexes which proceed through an azide radical. Spectra recorded periodically during the photolysis showed that isosbestic points at 276, 338, and 350 nm were maintained for 22% reaction. Continued photolysis resulted in a loss of the isosbestic points and a general decline of the absorbance throughout the ultraviolet region. Addition of an aliquot of the photolyzed solution, buffered to a pH of 5, to a 0.1*M* $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution indicated free azide ion was not present. However, the photolyzed solution did oxidize iodide ion to iodine. A comparison of the observed spectral changes with spectra of synthetically prepared $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ and $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ showed that the reaction product was the latter chloramine complex.

The quantum yields summarized in Table 1 were found to be independent of the concentration of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$,

TABLE 1. QUANTUM YIELDS OF $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ AT VARIOUS WAVELENGTHS

$10^3 \text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$	λ_{ex} , nm	$\phi \text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+ a, b}$
2.57	250	0.63
2.60	300	0.61
3.04	350	0.83
2.61	400	0.65

^aDetermined at 25° and in 0.1 *M* HCl.

^bValues obtained from extrapolation of plot of ϕ vs *d* vs. per cent reaction.

over the range 10^{-8} - 10^{-2} *M*, and independent of whether the anion was chloride or perchlorate ion provided the concentration of chloride ion, present as NaCl, was 0.1*M* or greater. Also the quantum yield of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ was not found to be O_2 sensitive. The quantum yields of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ obtained for 0.1 *M* HCl solutions containing 10^{-3} *M* $[\text{Ir}_3(\text{NH}_3)_9\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ saturated with air, argon, or nitrogen were the same within experimental error. The quantum yield of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ was found to be independent of the concentration of hydrogen ion. Quantum yields of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ formation at 300 nm, corrected for hydrolysis of the product, for solutions buffered to pH 5 with a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and containing 0.1*M* NaCl were the same as values obtained in 0.1 *M* HCl. However, the yield was found to show a pronounced dependence on the concentration of Cl^- .

A series of photolyses of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ in a 4 : 1 methanol-water glass at 77° K were carried out to trap reactive intermediates. Photolysis of a glass at 77° K containing 10^{-3} *M* $[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ or $[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ resulted in the appearance of a yellow-brown

color which disappeared on melting. Identical spectra of the intermediate were obtained with either the chloride or perchlorate salt of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ and in acidic, 10^{-3} *M* HCl, or neutral glasses. In an attempt to characterize the intermediate observed in a glass, a series of flash photolysis experiments were undertaken. The spectrum of the intermediate in solution was obtained by a point by point kinetic method which consisted of separate experiments at different wavelengths. The results obtained on the fluid system gave a spectrum with an absorption band at 400 nm, in good agreement with the spectra obtained for the methanol-water glass experiments.

A mechanism consistent with the steady state and flash photolysis of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ is given by eqs. 6-13.

or eq. 12, product I represents the intermediate observed in the flash photolysis. Neither the steady-state nor the flash photolysis data allow a distinction between chloride ion scavenging the coordinated nitrene, $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}^{3+}$, followed by a rapid reaction with hydrogen ion to form the chloramine or protonation of the nitrene prior to addition of chloride ion. However, this does not affect the kinetic analysis, since the quantum yields were found to be independent of pH.

Similar studies¹⁹ were made on the photochemical reaction of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$, which gave experimental results different from that of the iridium(III) system. For example, photolysis of aqueous hydrochloric acid solutions of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ results in the evolution of nitrogen and the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$. Furthermore, unlike the iridium(III) complex, the stoichiometry of the photochemical reaction of the rhodium(III) complex is wavelength dependent (Table 2).

TABLE 2. QUANTUM YIELDS FOR THE PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS OF $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$

Wavelength, nm	ϕ_{dec} mol einstein ⁻¹	$\phi_{\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}}$ ^b mol einstein ⁻¹	ϕ_{N_2} ^b mol einstein ⁻¹	ϕ_{N_2} mol einstein ⁻¹
250	0.31 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	< 10 ⁻⁵	
275	0.178 ± 0.006	0.096 ± 0.005		0.18 ^c
300	0.104 ± 0.004	0.053 ± 0.002		
320	0.054 ± 0.003	0.043 ± 0.002		
350	0.035 ± 0.002	0.034 ± 0.002	< 2 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.035 ^d

^aIrradiated in 1.00 *M* HCl

^bIrradiated in neutral solution

^cIrradiated in 0.020 *M* HCl

^dIrradiated in 0.0020 *M* HCl.

At 350 nm 1 mol of nitrogen and 1 mol of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ are formed per mole of complex decomposed. Azide ion is not detected in the photolyte, $\varphi\text{N}_3^- < 2 \times 10^{-4}$. As the wavelength of exciting light decreases, a second mode of reaction resulting in the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$ becomes increasingly important. Ion-exchange chromatography of solutions photolyzed at 254 nm indicated that the products of the photochemical reaction are $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$. The isolated yield of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$, 0.59 mol per mole of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ decomposed, is in excellent agreement with the value 0.60 obtained from the ratio of the rates of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ formation to that of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ decomposition.

The formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ is readily explained by a coordinated nitrene intermediate, as the immediate product of the photochemical event. However, it seems unlikely that $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$ is formed by a similar path. Extensive studies in our laboratory indicated that the aquo complex is not formed by the secondary photolysis of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$. Nor is photoaquation an adequate explanation, since azide ion is not detected in the photolyte. Thus, it was proposed that the formation of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3+}$ results from a redox process, which is most efficient in the charge-transfer region of the spectrum of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$. Such behavior is characteristic of azide ion and azido metal complexes.¹⁶ However, recent studies²⁰ report that the aquo complex does result from the secondary photolysis of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$. It is claimed that no evidence was found for the formation of Rh(II) and azido radical for irradiations of wavelengths longer than 214 nm, and that at all longer wavelengths the photochemical process involves a nitrene pathway.

There appears to be a very definite trend in the photochemistry of the cobalt(III), rhodium(III), and iridium(III) azidopentaammine complexes. In the case of cobalt, the photochemistry is predominantly redox. For rhodium and iridium only nitrene formation occurs. The plus two oxidation state becomes less favorable with increasing atomic number, shifting the CTM excited state to higher energy. According to the proposed model the CTM excited state of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ lies below the reactive azide state and only redox photochemistry occurs. With $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ and $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$, however, the CTM excited state lies near or above the reactive azide excited state and only nitrene formation occurs.

This trend in the photochemistry is also consistent with the increasing stability of the coordinate nitrene intermediate. As the size of the outer d orbitals increases with increasing atomic number, the $d\pi - p\pi$ interaction increases thus stabilizing the coordinated nitrene intermediate. This further suggests that nitrene formation is most important in the photochemical reactions of the second- and third-row transition metal azidopentaammine complexes. However, recent studies by Katz and Gafney²¹ show that the photochemical reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$ also takes place by a nitrene

intermediate. It is of interest to note that the Cr(II) oxidation state, like Rh(II) and Ir(II), in ammine complexes is much less favorable than is Co(II).

Reaction of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ with Bromide and with Hydroxide Ions. Research on the reactions of chloramine metal complexes is very limited, which is one of the reasons we²² decided to study in detail the kinetics and mechanisms of some of the reactions of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$. Two of the reactions (eqs. 14 and 15) investigated appear to involve the formation of

the nitrene intermediate $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}^{3+}$

The formation of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Br})^{3+}$ from $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^{3+}$ is found to be first order in $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^{3+}$ and independent of bromide ion in the range $0.02M < \text{Br}^- < 0.1M$ (Table 3). However,

TABLE 3. PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE FORMATION OF $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Br})^{3+}$ AND OF $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})^{3+}$ FROM $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^{3+}$

Effect of hydrogen ion on the formation of

$\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Br})^{3+}$, $\text{Br}^- = 0.05 M$, $T = 25^\circ$, eq. (14)

$\text{H}^+ \times 10^5$	$k_{obs} \times 10^3, \text{sec}^{-1}$
1.99	3.48, 4.11
4.26	1.79, 1.81
6.68	1.25, 1.24, 1.28
14.10	0.609, 0.617

Effect of bromide ion on the formation of

$\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Br})^{3+}$ ion, $\text{H}^+ = 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$, $T = 25^\circ$, eq. (14)

$\text{Br}^- \times 10^3$	$k_{obs} \times 10^3, \text{sec}^{-1}$
2.30	6.21, 6.25
5.00	6.68, 6.47, 6.81
7.50	6.95, 6.44
10.00	7.08, 6.87

Effect of chloride ion on the hydrolysis of

$\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^{3+}$, $\text{H}^+ = 3.72 \times 10^{-6} M$, 25° , eq. (15)

$\text{Cl}^- \times 10^3$	$k_{obs} \times 10^3$
1.00	7.33
3.00	3.90
5.00	2.43
7.00	1.92
10.0	1.39

Effect of hydrogen ion on the hydrolysis of $\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5$

$(\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^{3+}$, k_{obs} from initial rates, 25° , eq. (15)

$\text{H}^+ \times 10^{-5}$	$k_{obs} \times 10^3, \text{sec}^{-1}$
2.82	3.71
5.64	2.28
9.04	1.61
11.22	1.33

^a Each k_{obs} is average of three runs.

^b Each k_{obs} is average of several runs.

the rate of formation is pH dependent, and kinetic studies were carried out at $2 \times 10^{-5} M < H^+ < 14 \times 10^{-5} M$. A plot of $1/k_{obs} vs H^+$ is linear over the range studied.

The formation of $Ir(NH_3)_5(NH_2OH)^{3+}$ from $Ir(NH_3)_5(NH_2Cl)^{3+}$ is first order in iridium complex concentration when additional chloride ion is present. In the absence of additional chloride ion, the $\ln(A-A_\infty)$ vs time plot deviated from linearity. Reaction (15) is inversely dependent on chloride ion concentration and inversely dependent on hydrogen ion concentration. A plot of $1/k_{obs} vs H^+$ (obtained from initial rates) is linear.

A mechanism for the formation of $Ir(NH_3)_5(NH_2Br)^{3+}$ consistent with the results is given by equations (16) - (19).

Earlier studies report¹⁰ the acid ionization constant $K_1 = 1.26 \times 10^{-6}$, from a titration of a solution of $Ir(NH_3)_5(NH_2Cl)^{3+}$.

This rate law is of the same form as that reported¹⁰ for the hydrolysis of $Ir(NH_3)_5(NH_2Cl)^{3+}$. Also the limiting rates are similar, 0.025 sec^{-1} compared with 0.05 sec^{-1} found in this study. However, the earlier study did not distinguish between a nucleophilic attack by hydroxide ion (eq. 15) and a unimolecular chloride ion release of the deprotonated chloramine (eq. 17). The work reported here on the bromamine suggests that a unimolecular process may also be occurring with the hydrolysis of the chloramine. If the hydrolysis also goes by a unimolecular decomposition (i.e. a coordinated nitrene intermediate), then chloride ion would react with the coordinated nitrene intermediate.¹⁸ In such a case reactions run with added excess chloride ion should be slower than those run with initially no chloride ion present. Experiments do indeed show that the reactions run with excess chloride ion were much slower than those with no added chloride ion, (Table 3). This observation along with the earlier results¹⁰ of inverse hydrogen ion concentration dependence, supports the following mechanism shown by equations (20) - (22).

Much has been written^{5,7,10,18} on the stability of the coordinated nitrene intermediate. This enhanced stability of coordinated nitrene compared with free nitrene is attributed to $d\pi-p\pi$ bonding (from a filled d orbital on the metal to the empty p orbital of the

electron deficient NH). One resonance form of the protonated azido group, $Ir(N_3H)$, is similar to that of the coordinated chloramide.

In both cases the leaving group would take with it a pair of bonding electrons leaving an electron deficient nitrogen capable of interacting with a filled d_{xz} or d_{yz} orbital of the metal. This stabilization of the nitrene intermediate may allow the hydrolysis of the coordinated chloramine to proceed via a nitrene intermediate, whereas the hydrolysis of free chloramine involves a S_N2 process.²³

Conclusion

The experimental results summarized here afford strong evidence for the existence of metal nitrenes (as defined in the introduction section) as active intermediates. The stability of the reactive nitrene (NH) molecule is enhanced by coordination to a metal-ligand combination which permits back π bonding of the filled d orbital electrons into the vacant p orbital of the singlet nitrene. This requires that there be a delicate metal-ligand balance to permit electron back bonding of metal $\rightarrow$ nitrogen, but not electron transfer which would result in the formation of the well known amido complex. The results of our experiments are in accord with metal nitrene formation for (1) the reactions of $Ru(NH_3)_5N_3^{3+}$ and $Ir(NH_3)_5N_3^{3+}$ with acid, (2) the photochemical reactions of $Rh(NH_3)_2N_3^{3+}$, and $Ir(NH_3)_5N_3^{3+}$, (3) the reaction of $Ir(NH_3)_5NH_2Cl^{3+}$ with bromide and with hydroxide ions.

Acknowledgement

I thank the Indian Chemical Society for the invitation to present a summary of some of our research in the special publication honoring Professor Priyadarshan Ray on the occasion of his 90th birthday. I recall, even as a student, reading his excellent papers on coordination chemistry and I join other coordination chemists around the world in wishing him a happy birthday. My coworkers who are mentioned in our references are largely responsible for the research described, and I thank them for their help. This project has been supported by a grant from the National Science Foundation.

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